

Ethnomedicine for Cardiovascular Diseases by the Tribes of Adilabad District, Andhra Pradesh, India

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Abstract- The paper deals with 28 species of plants covering 27 genera and 22 families used by the tribes of Adilabad district, Andhra Pradesh, for curing cardiovascular ailments. Fabaceae is the dominant family with four species. Herbs are dominant with 10 species followed by trees (9 spp.). Leaf is used in a maximum of 9 practices followed by stem bark (7). Twenty five practices were found to be new.

Keywords: Blood pressure, Chest pain, Heart diseases, Adilabad district, Andhra Pradesh

I. INTRODUCTION

Cardiovascular diseases (CVD) refer to any disorders of the heart and blood vessels. The most common ones are disorder of the heart muscle, strokes, heart failure and those caused by high blood pressure (Olorunnisola et al., 2011). Worldwide, CVD is assuming an increasing role as a major cause of morbidity and mortality (Krisela, 2007). It is estimated at approximately 1.6 million deaths per annum worldwide (WHO, 2003). Between 1990 and 2020, the proportion of deaths from CVD is projected to increase from 28.9 to 36.3% (Gowri et al., 2011). Moreover, in terms of number of years of life lost, CVD is expected to jump in ranking from the fourth to first, while as a cause of premature death and disability, it will rise from fifth to first (Hennekens, 2000). The predisposing factors to CVD include cigarette smoking, elevated cholesterol, hypertension, obesity, physical inactivity and diabetes (Olorunnisola et al., 2011). Before the discovery of modern medicines, many plants have been used by humans in the management, treatment and the related complications of CVD. A number of plants are reputed to possess cardio protective properties, resulting in their use by traditional healers for treatment of chest complaints, high cholesterol, high and low blood pressure and general heart problems. Plants may serve as the alternative sources for the development of new anticoagulant agents due to their biological activities.

Adilabad district is situated between 77° 47' and 80° 0' of the eastern longitudes and 18° 40' and 19° 56' of the northern latitudes. It is bounded on North by Yeotmal and Chanda districts of Maharashtra, on the East by Chanda district, on the South by Karimnagar and Nizamabad districts and on the West by Nanded district of Maharashtra state. It ranks second among all the districts in the state in forest area occupying about 44.5 per cent (7218.86 Sq km). The total tribal population of the district is 495,794 (18.08%) (Census, 2011) and the main tribes are Gonds, Kolams, Koyas, Lambadas, Mannes, Naikpods, Pradhans, Thoties and Yerukalas. Though there are publications on different diseases exclusive studies on cardiovascular diseases on the tribes of Adilabad district were not observed resulting the present study.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Extensive ethnobotanical explorations were conducted in 42 tribal pockets with good forest cover in Adilabad district during 2006-2009. Knowledgeable informants including the *vaidyas* and elderly persons (42) of the tribal communities were interviewed and obtained information on the plants used for curing cardiovascular diseases. The knowledgeable informants were taken to the field and along with the collection of plants for the voucher specimens, the use of the plants as given by them were recorded. The voucher specimens were deposited in the Herbarium of the Department of Botany (AUV), Andhra University, Visakhapatnam.

III. ENUMERATION

The plants are enumerated and arranged in an alphabetical order with botanical name followed by family, vernacular name, locality, collector, voucher number, tribal informant, part(s) used, method, mode and duration of treatment. Plants and practices marked with an asterisk (*) are considered to be new or less known.

Allium sativum L. Amaryllidaceae, VN: Tellulli, Talamagudu, NSS 7638, Manne

Blood pressure: One or two raw garlic cloves are taken during meal time for about two weeks.

Aloe vera (L.) Burm. f. Asphodelaceae, VN: Kalabanda, Boath, NSS 8132, Naikpod

***Chest pain:** Mildly heated leaf pulp along with seed powder of *Strychnos potatorum* is given in one spoonful dose twice a day for three days.

Alpinia malaccensis (Burm. f.) Roscoe Zingiberaceae, VN: Dumpa rashtram, Kubeer, NSS 8268, Pradhan

***Blood pressure:** Leaves are ground with jaggery, made into dry pills and administered orally three pills each twice a day for one month.

***Heart diseases:** Leaves are ground with sesame seeds and made into small pills and administered two pills twice a day for 45 days.

Andrographis paniculata (Burm. f.) Wall. ex Nees Acanthaceae, VN: Nelavemu, Lohesra, NSS 7745, Thoti

Blood pressure: Whole plant is burnt and ash mixed with black pepper powder and honey and made into pills and administered two pills twice a day for about one month.

Arachis hypogaea L. Fabaceae, VN: Yerusanga, Jainoor, NSS 7406, Yerukala

***Blood pressure:** One twenty five gm of seed in two glassful of water is boiled until ½ original volume of water remains and this extract is taken twice a day for about a week.

Aristolochia indica L. Aristolochiaceae, VN: Nagasaram, Jannaram, NSS 8276, Gond

***Blood pressure:** Roots are ground with those of *Rauvolfia serpentina* and mixed with sugar candy and taken orally in two spoonful thrice a day for about 20 days.

***Chest pain:** Roots are ground with black pepper and the extract is administered in two spoonful once a day for five days.

Asparagus racemosus Willd. Asparagaceae, VN: Pillipinchara, Dandepalli, NSS 7226, Kolam

Chest pain: Root tubers are crushed with turmeric and filtrate is administrated in two spoonful twice a day for three days.

Balanites aegyptiaca (L.) Delile Zygophyllaceae, VN: Garachettu, Tanur, NSS 7522, Koya

***Blood pressure and *Heart diseases:** Seeds are ground with black pepper and made into pills and two pills are administered orally twice a day for about one month.

Barleria cristata L. Acanthaceae, VN: Gobbi, Kuntala, NSS 8136, Lambada

***Blood pressure:** Root decoction is administered orally in two spoonful twice a day for about one month.

Careya arborea Roxb. Lecythidaceae, VN: Kumbhi, Neradigonda, NSS 8216, Manne

***Chest pain:** Stem bark is ground with that of *Streblus asper*, *Gmelina arborea* and black pepper and the paste is made into pills of one gm weight. Two pills are administered twice a day for five days.

***Heart diseases:** Stem bark paste is administered in 2 spoonful twice a day for about 2 weeks.

Casearia tomentosa Roxb. Salicaceae, VN: Giridi chettu, Ichhoda, NSS 7652, Naikpod

***Chest pain:** Stem bark is ground with jaggery and the paste is made into pills of bengal gram seed size, is administered in two pills twice a day for five days.

Catharanthus roseus (L.) G. Don Apocynaceae, VN: Billa ganneru, Narnoor, NSS 7944, Lambada

Blood pressure: Tender leaves are cooked with dal and eaten as vegetable till cure.

Chloroxylon swietenia DC. Rutaceae, VN: Billu, Luxettipet, NSS 7762, Koya

***Blood pressure:** Stem bark decoction is administered in two spoonful twice a day for about 15 days.

Cucumis maderaspatanus L. Cucurbitaceae, VN: Potti budamkai, Bhainsa, NSS 7992, Kolam

***Heart diseases:** Tender fruit used as vegetable and said to be good for prevention.

Flacourtia indica (Burm. f.) Merr. Salicaceae, VN: Kanaregu, Tanur, NSS 7944, Pradhan

***Blood pressure:** About 10 cm long, thin root ground with four black pepper fruits in cow milk is administered once a day on empty stomach for three days.

Gmelina arborea Roxb. ex Sm. Lamiaceae, VN: Gummudu, Kerameri, NSS 7944, Lambada

***Chest pain:** Stem bark is ground with that of *Streblus asper*, *Careya arborea*, and black pepper and the paste is made into pills of bengal gram seed size, and two pills are taken thrice a day for five days.

Gomphrena serrata L. Amaranthaceae, VN: Gangavaili koora, Mudhole, NSS 8024, Manne

***Chest pain:** Whole plant juice is given in two spoonful twice a day for about 10 days, and also fine paste is applied on chest till cure.

***Heart diseases:** Tender branches cooked with dal and taken as vegetable frequently till cure.

Ipomoea fistulosa Mart. ex Choisy. Convolvulaceae, VN: Besharam, Mandamarri, NSS 7132, Naikpod

***Blood pressure:** Leaf juice with honey is administered in two spoonful twice a day for about three months.

Mimusops elengi L. Sapotaceae, VN: Pogada chettu, Nennel, NSS 7898, Koya

***Heart diseases:** Ripe fruits are eaten to prevent heart diseases.

Momordica charantia L. Cucurbitaceae, VN: Kakara, Bheemini, NSS 8088, Lambada

Blood pressure: Leaf paste is made into pills of bengal gram seed size and administered in doses of two pills twice a day for 10 days.

Senegalia intsia (L.) Maslin, Seigler & Ebinger Fabaceae, VN: Korinda, Koutala, NSS 8060, Naikpod

Chest pain: Root bark extract is administered in two spoonful twice a day till cure. Simultaneously root bark paste is plastered over the affected area.

Senna obtusifolia (L.) H.S. Irwin & Barneby Fabaceae, VN: Thantemu, Vemanalli, NSS 7222, Kolam

***Blood pressure:** One teaspoonful of leaf powder is taken orally with warm rice boiled water (*kanje*) twice a day for one to two months.

Senna tora (L.) Roxb. Fabaceae, VN: Tantepu, Kothapalli, NSS 7518, Pradhan

***Blood pressure:** Dried leaf powder is administered in one spoonful with a cup of warm rice boiled water twice a day for about 45 days.

Solanum americanum Mill. Solanaceae, VN.: Kamanchi pandu, Bejjur, NSS 7022, Koya

***Chest pain:** Whole plant poultice is applied on the chest.

Strychnos nux-vomica L. Loganiaceae, VN: Eser mushti, Dahegaon, NSS 8442, Manne

Blood pressure: Leaves, stem bark and fruits are ground with ginger and made into small pills of 0.5 gm and two pills are administered thrice a day for 10-15 days.

Tinospora cordifolia (Willd.) Hook. f. & Thomas. Menispermaceae, VN: Minaptheega, Jaipur, NSS 7066, Lambada

Blood pressure: Whole plant extract is given as a tonic.

Waltheria indica L. Malvaceae, VN: Nalla benda, Luxettipet, NSS 8604, Kolam

***Blood pressure:** Root bark decoction administered in two spoonful twice a day for about 20 days.

Ziziphus mauritiana Lam. Rhamnaceae, VN: Regu, Bellampalli, NSS 8544, Manne

***Blood pressure:** Stem bark decoction is administered in two spoonful twice a day for 15 days.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The paper deals with 28 species of plants covering 27 genera and 22 families used by the tribals of Adilabad district, Andhra Pradesh, for curing cardiovascular diseases viz., blood pressure, chest pain and heart diseases. Fabaceae is the dominant family with four species followed by Acanthaceae, Salicaceae, Cucurbitaceae (two species each) and others with one species each. Habit-wise analysis showed the dominance of herbs with 10 species followed by trees (9 spp.), shrubs (6 spp.) and climbers (3 spp.). Morphological analysis showed the maximum utilization of leaves in 9 practices followed by stem bark (7), root and whole plant (4 each), fruit and seed (3 each), root bark (2), and stem, tuber and clove (one each). Of the 28 species of plants blood pressure alone is cured by 15 species followed by six species for chest pain alone; two species each for blood pressure and heart diseases, chest pain and heart diseases and heart diseases alone and one species for blood pressure and chest pain. Of the total 32 practices 24 were found to be new or less known (Jain, 1991; Kirtikar and Basu, 2003; Jain and Jain, 2016). Plants used for similar purpose in different parts of India, Bangladesh, Malaysia, Indonesia, Morocco and Senegal are *Strychnos nux-vomica* by Chenchu and Yanadi tribes of Gundlabrahmeswaram wild-life sanctuary, Andhra Pradesh (Ratnam and Raju, 2004); *Allium sativum* by the folklore of Swat district, Pakistan (Hamayun, 2007), Paliyan, Pulayan, Dooby, Parayar, Asariar, Mannadiar, Sakiliar tribes of Dindigul district, Tamil Nadu (Samuel and Andrews, 2010), Kalanguya tribe in Tinoc, Ifugao, Luzon, Philippines (Balangcod and Balangcod, 2011), folklore of Sherpur district, Bangladesh (Ferdoushi et al., 2016), Malayali people of Pachamalai Hills, Tamil Nadu (Rajadurai and Ramanathan, 2016), folk medicinal practitioners of Jamalpur district, Bangladesh (Ahamed et al., 2018), people of Bangladesh (Uddin et al., 2019), Bouhachem Natural Regional Park (Rif of Morocco), Bni-Leit and Al-Oued districts of Morocco (Bachar et al., 2021), tribes and folklore of Erode district, Tamil Nadu (Kemila and Krishnaveni, 2023); *Catharanthus roseus* by Mullu kuruma tribe of Wayanad district, Kerala (Silja et al., 2008), Lushai tribes in North Cachar Hills district of Assam (Sajem and Gosai, 2010), Dimasa Kachari tribes of North Cachar Hills district of Assam

(Tamuli and Sharma, 2010), Sanger tribe of Sangihe Islands, North Sulawesi, Indonesia (Pandiangan et al., 2019); *Momordica charantia* by Hmar tribe of Cachar district, Assam (Nath and Choudhury, 2010), folklore of East Godavari district, Andhra Pradesh (Divya et al., 2015), Yanadi tribe of Sriharikota Island of Andhra Pradesh (Kumar and Suryanarayana, 2020); *Allium sativum*, *Momordica charantia* by Irula tribe of Coimbatore district, Tamil Nadu (Ganesan and Kumaresan, 2017); *Andrographis paniculata*, *Momordica charantia* by the Javanese-Malay community in Kampung Parit Jelutong, Batu Pahat, Johor, Malaysia (Ismail et al., 2018); *Allium sativum*, *Balanites aegyptiaca*, *Momordica charantia* by the communities living near Fathala Forest, Senegal (Diop et al., 2022) and *Ziziphus mauritiana* by the people of Raipura upazila of Narsingdi district, Bangladesh (Islam and Uddin, 2022).

V. CONCLUSIONS

It is important to conduct further scientific research on the medicinal plants used for cardiovascular diseases by the tribes, not only with the objective of discovering new and possibly more efficacious drugs, but also for scientific validation of the medicinal claims. This can offer the population a cheap alternate remedies and spur conservation efforts of these plants. No doubt the present information is undeniably useful, as ethnobotanical survey data and traditional knowledge of medicinal plants are one of the irreplaceable pools of knowledge, in which unplumbed information are stored. It is believed that with deeper research into the bioactive composition and mode of action of the chemical contents of these documented medicinal plants, a goal for finding important lead compounds for treatment of ailments and complications associated with heart diseases can indeed be achieved in future.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Ahamed, T., Koushik, M., Muhammad, I.K., Tahmina, N.M., Tanziba, A. and Rashedul, I. 2018. "Ethnomedicinal survey of plants used by the folk medicinal practitioner (FMP) in the Jamalpur sadar Upazila, Jamalpur district, Bangladesh". *Asian J. Med. Biol. Res.* 4 (4): 422-426.
- [2] Bachar, M., Houda, E.I., Yacoubi, Zidane, L. and Rochdi, A. 2021. "Ethnomedicinal and traditional phytotherapeutic plants used in Bouhachem Natural Regional Park (Rif of Morocco): Case of Bni-Leit and Al-Oued districts". *J. Pharm. Pharmacogn. Res.* 9 (3): 284-312.
- [3] Balangcod, D.T. and Balangcod, A.K.D. 2011. "Ethnomedicinal knowledge of plants and healthcare practices among the Kalanguya tribe in Tinoc, Ifugao, Luzon, Philippines". *Indian J. Trad. Knowl.* 10 (2): 227-238.
- [4] Diop, M., Diop, F.N., Dieng, S.D., Samb, A., Manga, G.E.D., Sané, A.P., Sène, M.B., Sambou, B., Goudiaby, A. and Diatta, E.A. 2022. "Ethnobotanical study of medicinal plants for treatment of diabetes and hypertension used in communities near Fathala forest, Senegal". *Ethnobot. Res. Appl.* 23(7): 1-15.

- [5] Divya, K., Roja, N.M. and Padal, S.B. 2015. "Ethno-Medicinal Plants used in East Godavari District, Andhra Pradesh, India". *Int. J. Pharmacol. Res.* 11: 293-300.
- [6] Ferdoushi, A., Mahmud, S., Rana, Md.M., Islam, Md.S., Abu, S.A.S. and Hossain, M.F. 2016. "A survey on medicinal plant usage by folk medicinal practitioners in different villages at Nalitabari Upazilla, Sherpur District, Bangladesh". *European J. Med. Plants* 11(3): 1-22.
- [7] Ganesan, C.M. and Kumaresan, G. 2017. "Ethnomedicinal approaches for treating various diseases by Irulas tribals, Konbanur village, Anaikattihills, the western ghats, Coimbatore district". *Kong Res. J.* 4(2): 1-8.
- [8] Gowri, J., Vijay, A.A., Achi, R.S., Archunan, G., Kalavathy, S., Sampath, K.S. and Vijaya, K.K. 2011. "Redemptive benefit of atorvastatin in the risk factors of coronary artery disease". *J. Pharm. Res.* 4(3): 627-629.
- [9] Hamayun, M. 2007. "Traditional uses of some medicinal plants of Swat Valley, Pakistan". *Indian J. Trad. Knowl.* 6(4): 636-641.
- [10] Hennekens, H.C. 2000. "Clinical and research challenges in risk factors for cardiovascular diseases". *Eur. Heart J.* 21: 1917-1921.
- [11] Islam, S. and Uddin, M.Z. 2022. "Study of ethnomedicinal plants used by the local people of Raipura Upazila of Narsingdi district, Bangladesh". *J. Plant Taxon.* 29(1):137-156.
- [12] Ismail, N.A., Sabrana, S.F., Mohamed, M. and Bakar, M.F.A. 2018. "Ethnomedicinal knowledge of plants used for healthcare by the Javanese-Malay community in Parit Jelutong, Batu Pahat, Johor, Malaysia". *AIP Conf. Proc.* 1-11.
- [13] Jain S. K. 1991. *Dictionary of Indian Folk Medicine and Ethnobotany*. Deep Publications, New Delhi.
- [14] Jain, V. and Jain, S.K. 2016. *Compendium of Indian Folk Medicine and Ethnobotany (1991-2015)*. Deep Publications, New Delhi.
- [15] Kemila, P. and Krishnaveni, C. 2023. "Ethnomedicinal survey on plants used by the tribes in Gunri panchayat of Sathyamangalam Taluk, Erode District, Tamil Nadu". *J. Non-Timber Forest Products* 30(2): 92-101.
- [16] Kirtikar, K. R. & Basu, B. D. 2003 (Reprinted). *Indian Medicinal Plants*. Oriental Enterprises, Dehra Dun, Uttaranchal.
- [17] Krisela, S. 2007. "The heart and stroke foundation South Africa heart disease in South Africa media data document". <http://heartfoundation.co.za/docs/heartmonth/HeartDiseaseinSA.pdf>
- [18] Kumar, B, and Suryanarayana, P. 2020. "Ethnomedicinal recipes for cardiac and hypertension properties from tribals of Sriharikota Island, Andhra Pradesh". *Int. J. Pharmaceut. Sci. Rev. Res.* 26: 166-170.
- [19] Nath, M. and Choudhury, M.D. 2010. "Ethno-medico-botanical aspects of Hmar tribe of Cachar district, Assam (Part I)". *Indian J. Trad. Knowl.* 9(4):760-764.
- [20] Olorunnisola, O. S., Bradley, G. and Afolayan, A.J. 2011. "Ethnobotanical information on plants used for the management of cardiovascular diseases in Nkonkobe Municipality, South Africa". *J. Med. Plant Res.* 5(17): 4256-4260.
- [21] Pandiangan, D., Silahi, M., Dapas, F. and Kandou, F. 2019. "Diversity of medicinal plants and their uses by the Sanger tribe of Sangihe Islands, North Sulawesi, Indonesia". *Biodiversitas* 20: 611-621.
- [22] Rajadurai, M. and Ramanathan, K. 2016. "Ethnomedicinal survey of plants used by Malayali community to treat coronary heart diseases in Pachamalai Hills". *Nat. J. Physiol, Pharm. Pharmacol.* 6: 336-339.
- [23] Ratnam, K.V. and Raju, R.R.V. 2004. "Folk medicine from Gundlabrahmeswaram wild-life sanctuary, Andhra Pradesh". *Ethnobotany* 16: 33-39.
- [24] Sajem, A.L. and Gosai, K. 2010. "Ethnobotanical investigations among the Lushai tribes in North Cachar Hills district of Assam, Northeast India". *Indian J. Trad. Knowl.* 9(1): 108-113.
- [25] Samuel, J.K. and Andrews, B. 2010. "Traditional medicinal plant wealth of Pachalur and Periyur hamlets Dindigul district, Tamil Nadu". *Indian J. Trad. Knowl.* 9(2): 264-270.
- [26] Silja, V.P., Varma, K.S. and Mohanan, K.V. 2008. "Ethnomedicinal plant knowledge of the Mullukuruma tribe of Wayanad district, Kerala". *Indian J. Trad. Knowl.* 7(4): 604-612.
- [27] Tamuli, P. and Sharma, P. 2010. "Ethno-medico-botany of the Dimasa Kachari of North Cachar Hills district of Assam". *Indian J. Trad. Knowl.* 9(4): 718-720.
- [28] Uddin, M.Z., Atiya, B.R., Farhana, Y.M. and Tahmina, H. 2019. "Ethnomedicinal plants for prevention of cardiovascular diseases in Bangladesh". *Bangladesh J. Plant Taxon.* 26(1): 83-95.
- [29] WHO, 2003. "The World Health Report-2003". <https://www.who.int/whr/2003/en/>